

Cyclic voltammetric studies of oxovanadium(IV) complex with 2,6-pyridine-dicarboxylic acid in aqueous medium

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Abstract : The cyclic voltammetric behaviour of mononuclear oxovanadium(IV) complex with 2,6-pyridinedicarboxylic acid (H_2dipic), $[VO(dipic)(H_2O)_2]$ has been studied at GCE working electrode in aqueous 0.2 M $NaClO_4$ and 0.2 M KCl as supporting electrolytes at initial pH 4.25. $[VO(dipic)(H_2O)_2]$ complex undergoes diffusion-controlled irreversible one electron oxidation reaction in the potential range +0.865 to +1160 mV vs Ag/AgCl for scan rate 25 to 500 $mV s^{-1}$.

Keywords : Cyclic voltammetry, electrochemistry, oxovanadium(IV) complex, 2,6-pyridine-dicarboxylic acid.

Introduction

Many transition and heavy metal ions play an active role in a number of various biological processes, being a component of several vitamins and drugs. Pyridinedicarboxylic acids and their derivatives belong to an interesting series of compounds with biological applications¹. Pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (dipicolinic acid) is present in nature as an oxidative degradation product of vitamins, coenzymes and alkaloids and is component of fulvic acids. It has frequently been cited in the literature as a plant sterilizing and water germicidal agent and an antioxidant for ascorbic acid in foods^{2a}. Pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid is almost unique to bacterial spores and may constitute as much as 15% of their weight^{2b}. Pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid is a desirable ligand because of its low toxicity and amphiphilic nature.

Results and discussion

The electrochemical behaviour of 4 mM oxovanadium(IV) complex, $[VO(dipic)(H_2O)_2]$ has been investigated at a glassy carbon (GCE) working electrode in aqueous 0.2 M $NaClO_4$ and 0.2 M KCl, as supporting electrolytes at pH 4.25. A positive scan initiated at 0.0 V in the potential range from 0 to +1300 mV vs Ag/AgCl reveals an irreversible oxidation peak with E_{pa} at +915 mV at scan rate 100 $mV s^{-1}$ (Fig. 1). The oxidation peak poten-

tial shifts positively from 865 to 975 mV in aqueous 0.2 M $NaClO_4$ medium and from 985 to 1160 mV in 0.2 M KCl medium, with increasing scan rate from 25 to 500 $mV s^{-1}$, showing that the oxidation of complex becomes more difficult with increasing scan rate³. Furthermore, the anodic peak current is significantly larger in $NaClO_4$ as compared to that in KCl medium at a given scan rate. Also, a plot of I_{pa} vs square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) gives a straight line passing through origin, suggesting that the anodic processes are diffusion-controlled³. The following reaction pathway may be suggested to explain the observed electrochemical data :

Experimental

$[VO(dipic)(H_2O)_2]$ complex was prepared according to method described earlier⁴ and its purity was checked by elemental analyses. The cyclic voltammetry was carried out with a BAS Electrochemical System Model EP-SILON instrument having an electrochemical cell with a three electrode system. The working electrode was a glassy carbon, platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode and a Ag/AgCl as a reference electrode. All the cyclic voltammetry experiments were done in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen achieved by purging the cell solution

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of 4 mM [VO(dipic)(H₂O)₂] in aqueous/0.2 M NaClO₄ (pH 4.25) at 100 mV s⁻¹.

with pure nitrogen gas (99.99%) for about 20 min. An inert atmosphere of nitrogen gas was also maintained over the cell solution during recording of the voltammograms. 2,6-Pyridinedicarboxylic acid, sodium perchlorate, and potassium chloride were received from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Pvt. Ltd. NaClO₄ and KCl were used as the supporting electrolytes. The pH of the solution was 4.25 (initial pH), and the colour of the solution was light green. All experiments were performed at 25 ± 0.2 °C.

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